

Career Aspirations of Female STEM Students

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ABSTRACT

The STEM gender gap is caused by the interaction of several complex and nuanced factors, all of which need to be considered when designing effective interventions. Providing students, parents and teachers with information about the broad range of career opportunities that STEM can offer is one of the factors frequently discussed in the literature. Addressing this information deficit is also identified as a specific action amongst the Recommendations on Gender Balance in STEM Education. The perception that STEM careers are not compatible with students' desire to work with people or on areas of societal benefit is a commonly held misconception that deters female students from considering STEM pathways. Dispelling this stereotype should form a key emphasis for STEM promotion and information campaigns; particularly those targeted at younger teenagers. This paper presents an account of the career aspirations of undergraduate and postgraduate female STEM students. The research forms part of an ongoing PhD study focussing on the key factors influencing women who do choose STEM careers. The students interviewed ($n = 21$) are nearing the end of their programme of study in STEM and are considering future career paths. Many have undertaken work placements or internships and have experienced varied career opportunities. Thus, they offer a unique perspective on the interests, motivations and career goals of young women in STEM. This perspective is largely unheard in current discourse, and it is anticipated that their insights will be useful in designing promotion campaigns aimed at encouraging more female students to consider STEM as a personally fulfilling, rewarding, and exciting career.

KEYWORDS

Gender gap, female student perspectives, key influences, career aspirations, interventions.

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Introduction

I always had people telling me that it (*engineering*) would be something that I would be good at and I think I didn't have an interest in it because I didn't know what it was to be completely honest.... I was never really educated on what it was and what I would be doing if I was doing it, you know?

This quote from Sophie (pseudonym), an engineering undergraduate interviewed as part of this study, highlights one of the many challenges underpinning the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) gender gap, namely a lack of awareness of STEM career opportunities. A survey of teenage girls in Ireland found that 87% of respondents stated a lack of information about STEM jobs as a barrier to a STEM career (iWish, 2021). Therefore, providing students, teacher and parents with information about the vast range of opportunities offered by STEM is an essential tool for addressing the imbalance.

The *Recommendations on Gender Balance in STEM Education* (Department of Education, 2022) considers STEM education from early childhood through to higher education. It discusses a STEM ecosystem where “families, early years settings, schools, policy, industry and society” (p.5) each have crucial roles to play in creating more gender balance. Four key areas for action, encompassing this ecosystem, are identified and this paper focuses on the fourth action; “Support a societal and cultural shift to address current barriers to gender balance in STEM” (p.6) which includes engagement campaigns to raise awareness of STEM careers.

This paper presents preliminary findings relating to career aspirations from an ongoing PhD research study exploring the commonalities, if any, amongst female STEM students. Career aspirations are one of the aspects being studied as it is anticipated that student insights will be beneficial in informing engagement campaigns.

Key Considerations for STEM Career Awareness Campaigns

Information campaigns aimed at raising awareness of STEM careers need also to address the main barriers deterring girls from choosing STEM. These include; gender stereotypes, confidence and interest. Multiple theories exploring these barriers are presented in research literature. No single theory uniquely captures the problem since the issues involved are complex and layered. The gender gap is best understood by considering the culmination of a range of interacting factors, at play from early childhood and intertwining at all stages and levels of girls' lives and experiences.

Barriers to STEM Entry

From an early age, girls are subjected to gender stereotypes. Parents with strong gender stereotypes around male/female roles, interests and abilities project these onto their children (Wang & Degol, 2017). Media portrayals of scientists and engineers as predominantly male, socially isolated and technology focussed (Cheryan et al., 2017) reinforce STEM stereotypes whilst a lack of female role models (Diekman et al., 2017) and little information about what STEM professionals actually do and why (Boucher et al., 2017) further exacerbates the issues. Within the wider environment, girls receive less encouragements from parents, teachers and peers to study STEM subjects such as physics (Francis et al., 2016). Thus, girls' perceptions of their place in STEM is framed from childhood and they begin to associate STEM with being a masculine domain in which they neither belong nor have the ability to succeed in.

Confidence and self-efficacy are significant factors in the STEM gender gap. Cheryan et al., (2017) highlight that female students of computer science, engineering, physics and maths report less confidence in their ability to succeed and note that even amongst students who

perform equally well in mathematics assessments, boys are more likely to rate their mathematics abilities as high compared with girls. Furthermore, girls are more likely to believe that innate intelligence is needed to succeed in STEM and are less confident in their own natural abilities (Wang & Degol, 2017). This attitude is replicated by teachers who tend to perceive girls' achievements in physics as being attributed to hard work whereas boys' achievements are attributed to natural ability (Francis et al., 2016). Thus, girls believe that they need to put more effort and work harder than their male peers in order to achieve the same result. To wish to pursue a career in STEM, students need to feel that they have the ability required but also an interest and motivation in the area. Having an interest is as important an indicator of career preference as aptitude (Wang & Degol, 2017). Interest and ability are related since lower confidence and self-efficacy results in lower interest in STEM and less motivation to pursue a STEM career. Interest is also heavily linked with a sense of belonging (Cheryan et al., 2017).

Boucher et al. (2017) discuss the STEM gender gap through the lens of communal goals – the desire to collaborate and help others. As noted by Boucher et al.'s (2017) findings girls highly favour communal goals and their underrepresentation in STEM can be viewed as being attributed to a misperception that STEM careers are not compatible with communal goals. They suggest that girls with communal goals are less likely to feel a sense of belonging in STEM and, thus, have less interest and motivation in pursuing STEM careers. This also seems to be borne out by a recent survey of teenagers' career aspirations. Results from the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) survey found 15 year-olds' career aspirations to be narrowly focussed on a small range of career options. In Ireland, 60% of girls and 49% of boys expressed a desire to work in one of 10 jobs. Despite a rapidly changing sociocultural and socioeconomic landscape, teenagers' career aspirations were also found to have changed little in the last 20 years (Mann et al., 2020). Career expectations were found to differ significantly by gender, even amongst boys and girls who achieved similar learning outcomes in PISA. The top two occupations favoured by girls were medicine and teaching – aligning with communal goals theory - whereas engineering and business management were top for boys.

Focus Areas for Interventions

Thus, interventions addressing the STEM gender gap need to be multi-faceted and appeal to girls on many different levels. Francis et al. (2016) discuss the need to dispel the image of STEM subjects such as physics as being a masculine and hard domain and of the importance of presenting STEM as a welcoming and accessible option for women. They highlight the negative impact of the lack of women in subjects such as physics and stress the responsibility of the media to portray positive representations of women in STEM. Wang and Degol (2017) also present the case for more female role models and for breaking down stereotypes. They recommend the need to communicate the relevance of STEM qualifications in real world applications and emphasise actions enhancing girls' interests as well as abilities. Efforts that encourage girls' sense of belonging in STEM are proposed by Cheryan et al. (2017). The need for role models whose communal goals are being satisfied by a career in STEM is discussed by Boucher et al. (2017) who also present the case for increased awareness of the relevance of STEM applications in addressing such communal goals. Diekman et al., (2017) outline how female role models perpetuate a sense of belonging while Cowgill et al. (2021) propose that interventions should demonstrate how women belong and are welcomed within STEM.

This research study is focussed on actions aimed at female students in second level education. It seeks to build on the recommendations in the existing body of literature by demonstrating, for example, how female STEM students are finding coherence between communal goals and career aspirations. The research participants provide rich insights into skillsets needed for

successful STEM careers and it is proposed that emphasising such skillsets may be of benefit in fostering female students' sense of belonging and interest in STEM.

Research Method

A qualitative research design, involving one-to-one interviews with female undergraduate and postgraduate students studying mathematics-intensive STEM programmes in University College Cork (UCC) or Munster Technological University (MTU), was implemented. Interviews were semi-structured with questions partially guided by theories exploring barriers to STEM entry as outlined in the previous section. Participants were asked about experiences in secondary school; career choices; college experience; hobbies and interests, and perspectives on the STEM gender gap. At the end of the interview participants were given an overview of theories being explored in the research study and invited to comment. Reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022) was used to explore factors influencing students' choice to study STEM in University and to identify what commonalities, if any, the students share besides their gender

To recruit participants, invitation to participate emails were sent to female students by lecturers in their departments. This email included a brief description of the rationale for the study and of how the research would be conducted. Interested students were asked to contact the student researcher for further details. Prior to interview, once the students had provided consent to participate, they were asked to complete a preliminary survey during which data on programme of study, secondary school and Leaving Certificate (LC) subjects were collated. This data is shown in the interviewee profile in Table 1 with the participants being identified by pseudonyms.

Table 1: Research Participant Profile

Student (Pseudonym)	STEM Programme of Study	University	Year of Study	Leaving Certificate STEM Subjects (Higher Level)
Alex	S	UCC	PhD	N/a
Alice	S	UCC	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry
Anne	SE	UCC	PhD	Maths, Biology
Caoimhe	E	MTU	3 rd	Maths, Chemistry
Caroline	M	UCC	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, Design and Communication Graphics (DCG)
Clodagh	E	MTU	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths
Emily	E	MTU	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths
Jade	M	UCC	4 th	Maths, Chemistry, Applied Maths, Biology
Jennifer	E	UCC	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, Biology
Kathryn	E	UCC	5 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry
Leah	E	MTU	4 th	Maths, Physics, Applied Maths
Lola	S	UCC	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry
Madeline	S	UCC	3 rd	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology
Molly	E	MTU	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry
Natalie	SM	UCC	3 rd	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths
Niamh	SM	UCC	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry
Roisín	S	UCC	PhD	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology
Sonia	SM	UCC	3 rd	Maths, Physics, Applied Maths, Engineering
Sophie	E	UCC	4 th	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Applied Maths, Biology
Úna	S	MTU & UCC (Joint)	Undergrad	Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Biology
Zoe	E	UCC	5 th	Maths, Physics, DCG

The interviewees programmes of study include: E (engineering, $n=10$); S (physics or computer science, $n=10$) or M (mathematics, $n=5$). Where students are studying e.g. mathematics and physics, they are included in both the science (S) and mathematics (M) categories shown in Column 2 of Table 1. As some of the students interviewed may be the only female in their class, it's not possible to breakdown the categorisation of students further as this may make the students identifiable and contravene ethical requirements to preserve anonymity of research participants.

Interviews were conducted online via Microsoft® Teams and were typically 50 minutes in duration. Students self-selected to participate and 21 third and fourth year undergraduate and postgraduate students were interviewed between January and May 2022. The interviews were recorded and once an anonymised transcription of the interview was created, the recordings were deleted.

The preliminary findings presented in this paper are drawn from thematically analysing student responses to questions asking them to describe their dream jobs, what attributes they felt were required to be a successful professional in their chosen field as well as insights students shared from experiences in a workplace environment.

Preliminary Findings

Three themes describing career aspirations were generated from the data. These are categorised as:

- Field; encompassing what type of workplace environment students would like to work in and why – including specific application areas,
- Skillsets; encompassing what attributes the students feel professionals need to work in the field and,
- Lifestyle, encompassing desirable features students are looking for as part of their career.

Table 2 shows a summary of these themes and lists the subthemes within each category.

Table 2: *Categorisation of themes relating to Career Aspirations*

<i>Career Aspirations</i>		
Field	Skillsets/Attributes	Lifestyle
Healthcare Applications	Problem Solving	Variety
Lecturing/Teaching	Teamwork	Travel
Industry/R&D	Communication	Autonomy
Humanitarian	Thirst for Knowledge	Work-life Balance
	Patience/Perseverance	Job Security
	Hard Working	

Field

18 of the students expressed a desire to work within one of fields shown in Table 2. The other three students described their dream jobs in terms of specific lifestyle aspects they sought from a career in STEM. Six students wished to work in the healthcare space, four hoped to pursue careers in lecturing/teaching, six intended to work in industry or research and development organisations and two had aspirations to work in the humanitarian sector.

Students who aspire to a career in lecturing highlighted the lack of female lecturers in their programmes of study. Jennifer, who is excited to be a female engineer and help break stereotypes, takes inspiration from this as;

I've always found that I'm quite good at explaining things to people and helping them. So I wouldn't mind being a lecturer.... I have that fantasy in my head 'cause like I've never had a female lecturer

The desire to “make a difference” was expressed by many students, Kathryn sees this as;
.....something that has a real life application....my project that I'm doing this year is looking at heart rate and seeing how that could help diagnose brain injury in neonatal intensive care units. I love that project.....I kind of like that application part

For some of the students, their dream to work in a particular field was informed by college work placement or relevant job opportunities they availed of during college. For others it was from their experiences during their programme of study. Caroline, for example, describes how a visiting lecturer came to speak with her mathematics class about opportunities in computational neuroscience. She tells of her dream to work in this field as it would satisfy her interests in both mathematics and the human brain. She describes how studying mathematics has taught her that “maths is just so practical and applicable to any kind of field.”

Skillsets/Attributes

As well as the career fields they would like to enter, the interviewees were asked what they believe are the main attributes needed to work in STEM. It's unsurprising that problem solving and analytical skills were most frequently cited by the students as these are core skills needed by STEM professionals.

However, the students equally highlighted communication and teamwork skills as key attributes. Alice believes she has good communication skills and she described how valuable this has been to her throughout her undergraduate years. For Alice the attributes of a good physicist are:

...self-belief, problem solving skills and good communication skills, which often doesn't go hand in hand with people who are really good at physics. Definitely communication is huge because, like, that's what science is built on basically - learning things off other people and new discoveries are found that way, you know.....I think it's just as important as being super intelligent is being able to communicate

Emily did work placement in industry where she was part of a maintenance team. She describes the importance of being able to communicate to everybody within the organisation when trying to troubleshoot;

Communication! It's a huge thing.....You don't think about this when you're going into engineering, but like Oh my God!, it's just all talking to teams and to people and different offices and stuff

Clodagh highlighted having good people skills as being essential throughout college, particularly when working in group situations. She says;

I think being able to work with people, definitely. Like in all the group projects I've had, the people I found the best are those who are good at interacting with people and just willing to help

Emphasising the necessity of such skillsets would be useful in fostering girls' sense of belonging in STEM, as discussed in the next section.

Lifestyle

Lifestyle factors were identified as a third subtheme within career aspirations. Financial security is frequently mentioned as one of the benefits of a career in STEM. Of all the participants in this research study, only three mentioned finance when discussing career aspirations. Only one student valued the financial security of a STEM career in and of itself. The other two students spoke of the benefits of STEM being financially lucrative in that it would enable them to finance hobbies or a desire to do humanitarian work.

A career providing variety and not “being in an office all day” (Caoimhe) were also valued by the students. Úna spoke of how, on her current work placement in a medical devices company, she saw that staff had the freedom to decide to structure their working day between laboratory and office activities and she valued this flexibility and autonomy.

Implications for Promoting STEM Careers and Lifepaths to Girls

Engagement campaigns to raise girls’ awareness of the diversity of career opportunities offered by STEM need to tackle all the barriers of entry faced by female students. The students interviewed for this research study have overcome several challenges in breaking down these barriers and are now positioned to see how STEM careers offer the opportunity to fulfil personal goals in richly diverse fields.

Fostering a sense of belonging needs to dispel stereotypical images of STEM professionals as males working in isolation. In contrast to this, the participants in this research study highlighted the importance of people skills, including teamwork and communication, as being essential attributes for STEM professionals. Emphasising these attributes, more commonly associated with women, would not only help girls feel a greater sense of belonging in STEM but may foster girls’ confidence in believing that they bring valued and necessary skills needed to optimise the use of STEM applications across the entire range of fields. As well as promoting the diversity of STEM career opportunities, it’s worthwhile to also promote the people skills needed for STEM jobs to reinforce to girls that they do fit within a STEM environment.

While the career aspirations of the research participants lay in several different fields, common amongst all the students was the vision of how their STEM qualifications could be applied in any area of their choice, in a manner satisfying their personal goals. The perception that STEM careers provide less fulfilling pathways for people with communal goals who wish to work in collaboration with and helping other is one of the most significant deterrents that needs to be addressed. In this research study, students who expressed communal goals found no incongruity between goals and STEM careers. Instead, they had identified clear pathways of how their STEM qualifications could be applied in diverse fields including healthcare applications, teaching, environmental challenges and futureproofing electronics systems. Not only did they recognise communal goals opportunities in STEM, they also saw how their identities could bring a significant contribution in their chosen fields.

Conclusions

The importance of female role models is widely cited in the literature. Greater collaborations between schools and universities, including opportunities for students – particularly in Junior Cycle (JC) – to collaborate with undergraduate and postgraduate female STEM students may encourage more girls to remain in STEM for Senior Cycle. Mentoring programmes where JC students can meet with and learn from the experiences of current university students may have significant benefit in fostering interest, motivation and belonging. As young professionals, female STEM students share ideals and values with teenage girls and are well positioned to highlight how they are finding personal fulfilment and rewarding opportunities as they plan the next stages of their careers. Not only would this provide JC students with an opportunity to see what’s involved in different programmes of study, it would help reinforce the real life applications of STEM. Parents and teachers also need be addressed by STEM information campaigns with different messages targeted at different groups; e.g. parents may place more value on the job security and financial benefits of STEM careers.

The insights and perspectives of female STEM undergraduate and postgraduate students offer many exciting opportunities in the development of interventions addressing the gender gap.

These insights are valuable in encouraging younger girls that not only do they belong in STEM but that they bring skills essential to ensure that STEM knowledge and applications are best utilised in a manner that benefits all of society.

References

- Boucher, K. L., Fuesting, M. A., Diekman, A. B., & Murphy, M. C. (2017). Can I work with and help others in this field? how communal goals influence interest and participation in STEM fields. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 901-901. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00901>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE Publications
- Cheryan, S., Ziegler, S. A., Montoya, A. K., & Jiang, L. (2017). Why are some STEM fields more gender balanced than others? *Psychological Bulletin*, 143(1), 1-35. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000052>
- Cowgill, C., Halper, L., Rios, K., & Crane, P. (2021). “Why so few?”: Differential effects of framing the gender gap in STEM recruitment interventions. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 45(1), 61-78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361684320965123>
- Diekman, A. B., Clark, E. K., & Belanger, A. L. (2019). Finding common ground: Synthesizing divergent theoretical views to promote women's STEM pursuits. *Social Issues and Policy Review*, 13(1), 182-210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sipr.12052>
- Department of Education (2022). *Recommendations on Gender Balance in STEM Education*. Retrieved from <https://assets.gov.ie/218113/f39170d2-72c7-42c5-931c-68a7067c0fal.pdf>
- Francis, B., Archer, L., Moote, J., DeWitt, J., MacLeod, E., & Yeomans, L. (2016). The construction of physics as a quintessentially masculine subject: Young People’s perceptions of gender issues in access to physics. *Sex Roles*, 76(3-4), 156-174. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-016-0669-z>
- iWish (2021). *2021 Survey of female students’ attitudes to STEM*. Retrieved from <https://www.iwish.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/I-Wish-2021-Survey-Report.pdf>
- Mann, A., Denis, V., Schleicher, A., Ekhtiari, H., Forsyth, T., Liu, E., & Chambers, N. (2020). *Dream Jobs? Teenagers’ career aspirations and the future of work*. Organization of economic cooperation and development. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/education/dream-jobs-teenagers-career-aspirations-and-the-future-of-work.htm>
- Wang, M., & Degol, J. L. (2017). Gender gap in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM): Current knowledge, implications for practice, policy, and future directions. *Educational Psychology Review*, 29(1), 119-140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-015-9355-x>